

Physical geomorphometry

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Abstract— Physical geomorphometry is introduced as a specific subfield of geomorphometry, investigating the land surface in terms of the basic principles, practices, and concepts of physics. The interconnected system of geomorphometric energies gives meaning to the summation, difference and ratio of basic geomorphometric variables. This explains the mutual relations of many well-established variables, indexes and equations and enables construction of new indexes expressing land surface (dis)equilibria. Conspicuous analogies between some aspects of physical geomorphometry and general relativity point to the possible wider scientific relevance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Geomorphometry is simply defined as quantitative analysis of the land surface. However, it is not only a set of geoscientific techniques but also a scientific field with its own object and theory. Geomorphometry investigates geometric properties of the land surface, dealing with their definition, measurement and computation, as well as interpretation. It is one of the most exact geoscientific disciplines, as the land surface is relatively static, directly observable, and measurable with increasing accuracy. The direct relation of the land surface with physical fields makes it one of the strongest predictors of surface processes. Geomorphometry has played a significant role in the ‘scientification’ of knowledge of the Earth – the transition from the classical idiographic geography (morphography) to the more nomothetic geo(morpho)logy, and to the prospective geomorphology, explicitly looking for the laws of Earth formation.

Geomorphometry has several facets that can be considered as subfields. Division into general and specific geomorphometry [1] is one of the most known. It is related to the field or object representation of the land surface in GIS databases and functionalities. Division into theoretical and experimental geomorphometry, as would be typical for the most developed sciences, is less pronounced. Despite conspicuous theoretical (definitions, laws and interpretations) and experimental aspects

(instrumentation, measurements and computations), a systematic tradition of setting up and performing geomorphometric experiments based on geomorphometric theory, with theory falsification by targeted experiments (the hypothetico-deductive scientific model), has not developed. Generally, definitions of geomorphometric variables and their relationships enable interesting theoretical predictions and interpretations, but a majority of geoscientific experiments use them only as incidental ingredients in specific predictive models of land surface processes and structures. Geomorphometric evaluation (if any) of these experiments is usually performed in terms of descriptive statistics (answering the question ‘what does it do?’) but avoids deeper theoretical explanations (answers to the question ‘why does it do?’). Already [1] specified some reasons in a paragraph “What is wrong with general geomorphometry today?” and, unfortunately, many of them persist until now [2]. Ignorance of the precise definition and theoretical interconnection of various geomorphometric variables is a serious problem.

Postulation and systematic development of physical geomorphometry (as a complement to the dominant praxis of descriptive geomorphometry) can help solve this. By ‘physical geomorphometry’ we mean basing analysis of the land surface on direct connection of (geo)physical fields and landform geometry. A shift from descriptive to physical geomorphometry would move our discipline from the idiographic to the nomothetic paradigm and develop its explanatory potential. Physical geomorphometry should be a significant part of theoretical geomorphometry and an engine for the development of a hypothetico-deductive approach in geosciences.

II. DEFINITION AND ROOTS

The adjective ‘physical’ appears in the names of various scientific subfields, however with different meanings. The name ‘physical geography’ refers to the material object of investigation (physical = natural geography as complementary to human geography). ‘Physical geology’, highly overlapping with physical

geography, is usually defined as a complement to (older-established) historical geology. In contrast, ‘physical chemistry’ and ‘physical biology’ (biophysics) refer to the principles, practices and concepts of physics used in chemistry and biology. By the analogy to these, we define **physical geomorphometry** as the specific subfield of geomorphometry, investigating the land surface (landforms) in terms of principles, practices, and concepts of physics, such as dimension, energy, work, force, thermodynamics and equilibria.

Relation of the land surface with gravity is crucial. Contours approximate equipotential levels of the gravity field [3] and therefore the majority of geomorphometric variables relate to this [4]. This is reflected in the interpretation and use of basic geomorphometric variables. Altitudinal differential is normally related to an energy (‘relief energy’). The sine of slope represents the downslope component of the gravity force, driving mass flow, whereas the tangent of slope is the ratio of downslope and normal components, determining the gravity stability of a slope. Profile and plan curvatures are responsible for the acceleration/deceleration and convergence/divergence of gravity flows. Interaction with other physical fields (solar radiation, wind, tectonic stress) is also very important and reflected in some geomorphometric variables (e.g. topographic exposure to wind, solar radiation and so on).

Basic physical-geomorphometric variables are used in various physically-based indexes and models of land surface processes. Topographic wetness index [5], topographic LS factor in the universal soil loss equation [6], unit stream power equation [7] and diffusion equation (e.g. [8]) are among the most widely used. Attempts to build conceptual (physical) interconnections of various variables and indices exist, but so far, they lack systematic character and experimental verification. Definition of the LS factor based on unit stream power [9] is one example. Unification of the influence of plan and profile curvature on soil erosion [10], generally described by [4] as the first and second basic mechanisms of flow accumulation, is another one. The majority of similar integrating concepts concern specific geomorphic processes, expressed as mass balances (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Basic physical categories related to geomorphometric variables. Energy, force and work can be considered as linked, most general physical categories. The various physical dimensions of mass balance point to physical specificity.

Mass balance results from dynamics – the effect of forces on motion. To apply a force, an amount of energy is required. And energy transferred by force produces geomorphic work in land

surface change, a long-term consequence of mass balance. Geomorphometric variables are most frequently interpreted in relation to the mass balance, but an energy / work interpretation (expression by the same physical dimension – joules) is more suitable for building a unified geomorphometric theory.

III. SYSTEM OF GEOMORPHOMETRIC ENERGIES

Fig.2 presents a system emergent in our earlier works [12] [2] [13] and fully derived in [11], where its effectiveness was tested and demonstrated for physically based land surface segmentation. The revealing of interconnected energetic (work) expressions of basic geomorphometric variables is the main achievement.

Figure 2. System of geomorphometric energies. More explanation in text.

LGE_{unit} is the potential gravity energy of a unit volume ($1m^3$) of material per 1 m altitude difference ($LGE_{unit} [kg.m^2.s^{-2}] = acceleration\ due\ to\ gravity \cdot 1m^3 \cdot density \cdot 1m$). Global, regional and local potential energies differ in the basis for the elevation difference: z – elevation above sea level, z_{rel} – relative elevation above a local base of erosion, $\Delta z = z_{max} - z_{min}$ in a window.

All local energies have the value of the given geomorphometric variable because LGE_{unit} as well as d (unit distance = 1 m) and A (unit area = $1m^2$) do not change the energy value (they only give it physical dimension). Geomorphometric energy for two basic geomorphic processes is represented by sine of slope (S), determining potential energy of surface for mass flow (PES), and by mean curvature (k_{mean}), corresponding to diffusion energy. Changes in PES can be concordant or discordant with the gravity field. Concordant changes directly influence gravity flows: the sum of this energetic effect is expressed by difference curvature (k_d). Gravity discordant change of PES is determined by geodesic torsion of contour line ($(\tau_g)_c$, the principal representative of the group of twisting curvatures

[2]). Gravity concordant changes of *PES* include energy for acceleration of flows, determined by normal slope line curvature ($(\mathbf{k}_n)_s$, the principal representative of the group of profile curvatures) and energy for flow concentration, determined by normal contour curvature ($(\mathbf{k}_n)_c$, the principal representative of the group of plan curvatures). The integral effect of various curvature energies on land surface processes and stability can be estimated by Casorati curvature (\mathbf{k}_c).

Our energetic analysis revealed fundamental differences of some similar, frequently used local variables. Interpretational ambiguity exists in the use of $\sin S$ and $\tan S$. The last can be correctly used in the stability term (ratio of gravity forces). However, when investigating dynamics powered by the downslope component of gravity force, $\sin S$ (*PES*) is the only correct choice. $\tan S$ only expresses projection of *PES* into the map (and is infinite for vertical scarps). Similarly, plan curvature of [14] and elevation Laplacian used in the diffusion equation express only *projected* concentration and diffusion energy.

Endogenous and exogenous work and relief brake force, derived in [12], can be a basis for conceptualization of regional energies: further work including multi-scale and hierarchical influences is needed on these. Local variables express energies immediately available for processes; regional variables reflect either long-term energetic potential or past geomorphic work. In this way, minimum endogenous work was derived as a function of the elevation of an envelope surface represented by maximum elevations (\mathbf{z}_{\max}), in windows the size of topographic grain. Minimum past exogenous work corresponds to Glock's available relief and can be estimated as the maximum of z_{rel} in the same window size – $(z_{rel})_{\max}$. The ratio of $(z_{rel})_{\max}$ to half of the topographic grain (*TG*) defines the braking energy of movement across the land surface (as a regional analogue of *PES*).

Such energetic interpretation of basic geomorphometric variables enables their direct comparison and systematic evaluation. Consequently, the homogeneity of basic geomorphometric variables defines a hierarchy of states of local geomorphic equilibria: static equilibrium, steady state, and non-steady state dynamic equilibrium. They are local attractors of landform development reflected in the geomorphometric tendency to symmetry (horizontality, various types of linearity, and curvature isotropy: all are types of gravity concordance). Specific indexes characterizing various (dis)equilibrium states can be derived: Index of Steady State (ISS – [12]) and Index of Slope Energy Disequilibrium (ISED – [2]) are examples.

IV. GREAT ANALOGIES (INSTEAD CONCLUSIONS)

'Pluralism and open discussion, even speculation, need to be allowed.'
(from the 'Rules of science' – [15])

Some analogies between the outlined fundamentals of physical geomorphometry and basic concepts of modern physics can be found. They can be an inspiration for the solution of some

ongoing problems in geoscientific modelling and perhaps even in physics. An analogy between general geomorphometry and general relativity provides a foundation. Both arise from field theory – 2D in the case of geomorphometry (land surface) and 4-D in relativity (universe). Both the land surface and the universe are curved. An advantage of geomorphometry is that we can directly investigate this curvature of the 2D land surface embedded in 3D space. In the case of the universe, we lack this extra dimension and can only hypothesize about the higher dimensions in which space-time is embedded.

A. Geometry = energy

General relativity postulates an equivalence of the geometry (curvature) and energy of spacetime [16]:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}$$

where (to simplify) $G_{\mu\nu}$ is spacetime curvature, $\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$ represents the cosmological constant (interpreted now as a manifestation of dark energy) and $8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}/c^4$ represents all energy (including matter). An analogous equation can be constructed from the local geomorphometric energies:

$$k_c + \sin S = ILGE$$

where $ILGE$ ($\geq LGE_{\text{unit}} \cdot \sin S$) is the 'Integral Local Geomorphic Energy' including the combined energetic effect of slope and all curvatures. This is equivalent to the sum of potential geomorphic work (both constructive and destructive, disregarding sign). It can be derived simply from the assumption that work is energy transferred to or from an object via the application of (e.g. gravity) force along a displacement. As curvature elongates the trajectory between two points, it increases the work and the energy. An imaginary 2-D observer on the land surface can directly investigate its curvature (smaller observable energy), but not its slope (for him, it is the bigger 'dark energy'). This analogy is in line with physical concepts of the existence of higher dimensions around 4D space-time.

B. Unified field theory and multidimensionality

Unification of the four fundamental forces into a unified field theory (one background field – energy) is one of the biggest challenges of modern physics. In geomorphometry, the basic energetic field (altitudinal: gravity) has long been known. However, the specific background energies of basic land surface processes such as mass flow, its acceleration or concentration, and diffusion processes are defined as an interconnected system for the first time in [11]. The system can be derived relatively simply by a 3D observer of the 2-D land surface. For the imaginary 2-D observer it would be a hard task, similar to a 4-D observer looking for a unified field theory in the more-dimensional reality of the Universe.

C. Problem of infinity

The definition of projected geomorphic energies is important for the practical design of geoscientific experiments. In an energetic interpretation, variables expressing unprojected energy should be preferred, avoiding prediction of infinite projected energies. Infinity is generally a big physical problem – nothing material should be infinite. Revelation of projected geomorphic energies supports the idea that the theoretically infinite density of black holes could also be perceived as a projection of finite density objects from the more-dimensional reality into our 4D space-time.

D. Arrow of time

A large majority of geomorphic processes operate in the slope gradient direction. This is trivial for the 3-D observer of the 2-D land surface. However, the 2-D observer (for which the slope is impalpable dark energy) can be surprised that all processes are unidirectional. In his 2-D world, nothing can move upslope, excluding strange diffusion processes. It could be an analogy of the physical problem of the ‘arrow of time’ in our 4D space-time. Unidirectional passage of time in the macro-world corresponds to the principally asymmetric mass flows that seem incomprehensible for the 2D observer. Time symmetry in the micro-world corresponds to diffusion geomorphic processes that enable upslope movement of some particles (against gravity – analogous to ‘time’s arrow’) although general downslope movement is a result of mass balance.

E. Fundamental consequences

Borrowing various physical and general scientific concepts, physical geomorphometry can improve geoscientific research. However, the analogies described suggest that the benefits could be mutual. They support hypotheses about the fractal-like essence of some natural laws and structures over various hierarchical levels of reality (e.g. [17]), although scale limits can exist [18]. The basic concept of physical geomorphometry introduced here could be part of a wider scientific law: having the benefit of studying lower-dimensional reality by a higher-dimensional observer, physical geomorphometry can be an inspiration for multidimensional physical concepts of the Universe (where the observer has no such privilege).

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